

Incorporating Green Supply Chain Management into an Incohate Eco-Industrial Developments: A Case Study Based on 2 Exemplars

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Abstract

Environment protection is an emerging concept these days. Protecting the depletion of the ozone layer, controlling global warming, forest fires are heard now and then. There is a need for Industrial ecology, which is an emerging concept for the establishment of ecologically sustainable industrial development in India these days. Optimizing materials, use of eco-friendly raw material, conservation of energy and green supply chain is a basic industrial ecology strategy.

The hyperlocal farm in Mumbai has developed an embryonic eco-farming industry by delivering freshly-harvested, leafy greens right to doorstep by applying an integrated approach to green supply chain management. Another innovation is an incubator lab at IIT- Delhi called kriya labs have found an alternative to stubble burning in the fields to protect the environment. They developed an eco-friendly industry that manufactures tableware. This paper describes the hyperlocal farm and kriya labs and their green supply chain management. After gathering the facts about the two companies, the paper illustrated their green supply chain models and arrived at some conclusions.

Keywords: Environment Protection, Green Supply Chain Management, Eco-friendly Industrial Developments, Energy Conservation.

Introduction

1. Green Supply Chain Management

SCM is defined as a concept in the material and transportation management approach using the traditional purchasing and logistics functions. It starts from the earth, then moves to the manufacturers, distributors, retailers and end customers. It involves several activities, like planning, product design and improvement, manufacturing, assembly, transportation, warehousing, distribution and customer service.

GSCM has been considered in both environment-focussed and SCM literature. The scope of GSCM involves establishing integrated green supply chains from the supplier to customer through the manufacturer, up to reverse logistics and recycling.

2. Evolution of Green Supply Chain Management

2.1 Understanding of Green Supply Chain Management

Green supply chain management is an Amalgamating green thinking and Supply chain management right from the product design to the recycling with an aim to protect environment.

2.2 Why Should Companies Go Green?

Sustainability is the reason why companies go green as resources are to be preserved for future generations. Another reason is that the consumers are going back to their roots and they increasingly prefer to purchase products that are free of toxins, produced with a minimum of pollution, and with a minimal environmental impact.

3. Major Concepts of the Green Supply Chain Management from the Literature

Green Supply Chain Management in Business

Traditional supply chains move from the raw material state to the end product the customer receives (cradle to grave). The concept of green is represented by eco-friendliness, social justice and economic development and health. The concept of 'green' does not only mean reduced waste and pollution; rather, it strives toward sustainable industry. Green industry considers energy conservation; material purchasing; processing, packaging, delivering and marketing the product; and reusing, recycling, usage and the waste cycle.

3.1 Green Product Design

Smart green design creates products that use less energy and natural resources; products that can be recycled easily or reused; and products that promote energy and materials efficiency in consumers' lives.

3.2 Green Materials Management

Green materials management is a way of substituting less hazardous activities or materials for more harmful ones.

3.3 Green Manufacturing Processes

Green manufacturing processes consist of three main phases, as follows: resource utilisation decrement, waste decrement and emission decrement. The goal of green manufacturing processes is the reduction of the consumption of harmful substances and other resources with the aim of minimising the total amount of waste in the manufacturing phase indirectly by decreasing energy and resource utilisation (Srivastava, 2007).

3.4 Green Distribution and Marketing

Green marketing can be defined as the promotion or advertising of products, changes in production processes or packaging changes that are weighed in terms of environmental criteria.

3.5 Reverse Logistics

Another significant component of GSCM, has the objective of collecting, distributing and managing products until they are delivered to customers. RL have been used in dealing with unsold stock and warrantee returns. It includes the recycling, reusing and remanufacturing of materials.

Literature Review

- Factors for Implementing Green Supply Chain Management in the Construction Industry by Mochamad Agung Wibowo, NaniekUtamiHandayani: This paper proposed a conceptual

framework for GSCM implementation in the construction industry. By applying the GSCM perspective, this study contributes to developing a GSCM standard in the Construction Industry.

- Green Supply Chain Management – Benefits Challenges and Other Related Concepts by Nandini Gajendrum: Green Supply Chain Management is an evolving concept and is still in its nascent stages. The study of the literature on GSCM and its benefits adds to a better understanding of the concept while a study of the challenges that lay ahead for the field make it very evident that GSCM has major prospects in the industry.
- Green supply chain management: a review and research direction by Noor Aslinda Abu Seman, Norhayati Zakuan, Ahmad Jusohand MohdShoki Md Arif :The purpose of this paper is to discuss a view of the incorporation of GSCM literature in a developed countries and developing countries.

Research Gap

The review of literature revealed that there were many studies that have taken place on the concept of green supply chain management. The current study is on the 2 companies that have integrated green supply chain management method to increase their returns on one side and also contribute to the ecology on the other side.

Need and Significance of the Study

Green supply chain management is an evolving concept and is still in its nascent stages. Though it is mandatory for every company to contribute to the ecology, many companies are still in a dilemma to integrate the concept of “Green” in their processes. Hence a study was needed to understand 2 companies that integrated green supply chain management in their processes to contribute to the ecology.

Objectives

- To understand the role played by the green supply chain management as a key tool to ease the way of doing business.
- To understand the various concepts involved in the green supply chain management.
- To understand the green supply chain management that is taking place in the Hyper local farm and Kriya labs.
- To understand the contribution made by the green supply chain management in elimination of waste and also the contribution made to the returns.

Research Methodology

The research is in the nature of a case study. Facts have been taken from the companies’ websites and other reference links. Data is collected and presented as it is. Reference about green supply chain management is taken from websites and research articles.

Analysis of the Study

1. Herbivore farm, Mumbai

Joshua Lewis and Sakina Rajkotwala from Mumbai were fed up with the routine IT jobs and were concerned about their health in the aspect of the food that they are consuming and the place it is coming from Hence, decided to take a big step after a visit to Auroville in Puducherry in 2017. Inspired by Krishna McKenzie, a native of England, who’s “honouring Mother Nature through local food.” They both got down to business with Herbivore Farms, Mumbai’s first hyperlocal, hydroponic farm. Today, the farm grows 2,500 plants, and sells fresh, organic vegetables to customers across Mumbai for a monthly subscription of 21 \$.

- **Year of Starting:** 2017
- **Location:** Andheri East, Mumbai.
- **Produce:** Super healthy varieties of leafy green vegetable like Swiss chard, kale, rocket and lettuce.
- **Method of cultivation:** Hydroponic.
- **Green Supply Chain Management**

Herbivore Farm is spread over 1,000 sq. Ft, and grows over 2,500 kinds of plants in a temperature-controlled indoor setting. Hydroponic method (growing without the use of soil) is used to grow their vegetables which makes them stand out among other farmers.

1.1 Green Product Design

The product chosen by this hyper local farm itself is growing Green leafy vegetables that are free from harmful chemicals and fertilizers.

1.2 Green Materials Management

The vegetables are grown in a clean environment, without pesticides, to make them 100 percent safe.

1.3 Green Manufacturing Process

The entire hyperlocal farm uses up to 80 percent lesser water and 0% soil to grow the produce as it uses a “recirculating irrigation system”. The water in which the plants are grown contains macro and micro-nutrients that facilitate the growth of the plant.

1.4 Green Distribution and Marketing

Harvested vegetables are delivered to customer’s homes in a few hours, maintaining freshness, nutrition, and flavour. To retain the consumers and make sure they like the produce, the farmers give leafy vegetables freely.

1.5 Reverse Logistics

The leafy vegetables are harvested as per the consumer’s requirement every morning and are packed in boxes to avoid the polluted air and then sent to the consumers by a delivery boy. In order to preserve the freshness in the leafy vegetables and also not to lose its nutrient values, the crops are soon delivered to the consumers as soon as they are harvested.

2. Kriya Labs, Delhi

Kriya Labs develops products and processes to produce highly affordable, qualitative and eco-friendly value added products from waste natural materials/fibres. Their strategy, broadly, is to add an economic and commercial value to the agricultural residue by making it an asset to the farmers while creating markets for rice straw.

The farmers in Haryana and Punjab burn the straw after the crop is harvested and dried. The smoke from the incineration is causing air pollution and is effecting the farmers and their families.

- **Year of Starting:** 2014
- **Location:** IIT, Delhi.
- **Produce:** Eco friendly Tableware.
- **Green Supply Chain Management**

The farmers are facing health issues and when approached by the kriya labs, they have agreed to sell their straw for a compensation around Rs.4000-Rs.5000 per acre.

2.1 Green Product Design

The rice straw is a natural waste that comes from the paddy fields after it is dried and the rice is beaten out.

2.2 Green Materials Management

The material is collected from the fields and taken into the factory to process it which is 100% natural.

2.3 Green Manufacturing Process

The rice straw is chopped down into small pieces and then it reaches the main unit where it will be washed and bleached using bio-degradable chemicals then a steam cooking process is done for one-two hours and then make a semi solid paste of the straw. The pulp is further processed with chemicals to make it ultra-pure. An edible adhesive is mixed to bind the pulp together and tableware is made out of it.

2.4 Green Distribution and Marketing

The finished product is sent to the tableware dealers for sale.

2.5 Reverse Logistics

The rice stubble is collected from the fields and then sent to the factory for further processing to make it into a finished good. The product is 100% biodegradable hence can be used for any purpose.

Findings

- Green supply chain management is taking place both at the herbivore farm and also kriya labs in terms of green product design, green materials management, green manufacturing process, green distribution and marketing and reverse logistics.. The raw material and the processes chosen are 100% natural and biodegradable.
- The companies are doing grate in terms of profits too and being rewarded for eco-friendly start-up initiations.

Conclusion

In order to contribute to the environment, initiatives were taken by 2 companies by involving “Green” into their product and processes. With the aim to control the pollution and promote healthy living, more companies like herbivore farms and kriya labs should come forward and take the initiation to go green to protect our planet.

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